

Maternal vitamin A deficiency in a settled Ariaal community in northern Kenya:

A direction for future research

A paper submitted to the *Journal of Development Alternatives and Area Studies*

Submitted by

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March 15, 2006

Abstract

Sedentary agriculture provides opportunities for pastoralists in East Africa, especially for poor families with few animals. Yet nutritional consequences of settlement are complex calling for the study of clinical and subclinical markers of micronutrient deficiencies. This paper presents results from 2004 and 2005 night-blindness surveys conducted among breastfeeding women in a settled agro-pastoral Ariaal community in Marsabit District, Kenya. Based on interviews using a modified version of the algorithm suggested by the World Health Organization (WHO), we found an extremely high prevalence of maternal night-blindness, a clinical sign of vitamin A deficiency (VAD). Since vitamin A is essential for a variety of bodily processes, notably vision, cellular differentiation, growth, immune responses, and reproduction, these findings pose serious implications for maternal health and children's survival, health and growth. This paper concludes with a suggestion for a minimally invasive follow-up study of maternal VAD using biochemical markers in dried blood spots obtained by finger-prick.

About the author

Masako Fujita is a doctoral candidate in Anthropology at the University of Washington (UW). She studies women's health with an interdisciplinary approach, borrowing theories and methods from fields of anthropology, demography, evolutionary biology, and public health. Prior to coming to UW, she studied at the University of Victoria, British Columbia, Canada where she obtained BA and MA in Anthropology.

Introduction

Livestock-keeping peoples of the world are increasingly shifting to more sedentary subsistence strategies based on agriculture, milk marketing, or wage-earning in response to ever more restrictive conditions due to population pressure, loss of grazing lands, political insecurity, and increased wealth disparity resulting from the commoditization of the pastoral economy (Fratkin, 1991, 1997, Fratkin and Roth, 2005). Relocation, migration, and subsistence change for pastoral peoples may be beneficial with respect to improved access to cash economy and amenities such as education and health-care, and/or increased governmental administrative efficiency. However, an unplanned consequence may include dietary changes with potential adverse effects on the population's health (for review see Fratkin et al., 2004; Kuhnlein and Receveur, 1996).

Sedentarization triggers a variety of changes, simultaneously and complexly affecting population's diet and health. For example, among Ariaal and Rendille in northern Kenya, sedentary agriculture permits steadier maternal food intake relative to nomadic mothers (Fujita et al., 2004, 2005). Yet, children in the same populations show impaired growth in settled communities relative to a nomadic pastoral community (Fratkin et al., 1999; Nathan et al., 1996; Roth et al. 2005). Additional studies also indicate less favorable health status of settled women, relative to nomadic mothers' health status (for reviews of this argument see Nathan et al., 1996; Sellen, 1996). However, most studies of nutritional and health consequences of sedentarization predominantly focus on anthropometry. This can provide insights into macronutrient (protein-calorie) status, but can tell us little about micronutrient status of the population.

Micronutrient deficiencies such as VAD have adverse health and functional consequences in the presence or absence of protein-calorie malnutrition. Thus they can be

dismissed in a research study dependent on anthropometry. This paper takes the position that the effects of sedentarization can be better understood by incorporating micronutrient status population markers. To support this claim, this paper presents preliminary data from 2004 and 2005 night-blindness (XN) and dietary recall surveys to delineate VA status of women in a sedentary agro-pastoral Ariaal community in Marsabit District, Kenya. Before presenting the data, the following sections provide a brief overview of the significance of VA to human health.

Roles of VA and VAD

VA performs crucial roles in a variety of bodily processes, notably vision, skin and mucosal integrity, innate and adaptive immune responses, cellular differentiation, growth, and reproduction (McLaren and Frigg, 2001). Until recently, only severe VAD, identified by xerophthalmia, the clinically manifested impairment of eye function and structure, was considered relevant to public health, primarily as a disease of preschoolers (Mamdani and Ross, 1989). It is now known that clinical VAD is only the tip of a large iceberg (MI & UNICEF, 2004). Even asymptomatic or subclinical VAD, assessed by biochemical parameters such as serum retinol ($<0.7\mu\text{mol/L}$), compromises immune function and is associated with a 25-30% elevated risk of infectious disease and death (MI & UNICEF, 2004; Sommer and West, 1996). Underscoring the magnitude of VAD as a cause of death, globally 16-21% of all children under five years of age are immuno-compromised by VAD, suffering increased rates of death from diarrhea, measles, and malaria (Black, 2003; WHO, 2004). Furthermore, it is now clear that women of reproductive age are equally or more at risk of VAD (Miller et al., 2002; West, 2002). This is problematic not only because women suffer but also because deficient mothers produce breastmilk with low retinol concentrations, compromising their nursing children's VA status (Miller et al., 2002).

VA is a fat-soluble vitamin, an essential micronutrient that humans must consume because we cannot synthesize it in our body. VA is the generic term for a class of compounds which possess the biological activity of the vitamin, including pro-vitamin A (proVA) carotenoids, preformed retinol, and its active metabolites. Retinol can be found in foods of animal origin, such as eggs, butter, cheese, milk, and liver. Breastmilk is an important source of retinol for children. ProVA carotenoids can be found widely in foods of both animal and plant sources. Common plant sources are dark and bright colored vegetables and fruits, such as carrots, pumpkins, dark green leafy vegetables, and mangoes. Retinol is superior to carotenoids as VA, because it is more bioavailable, or readily biologically available. This is because carotenoids are less absorbable in the human intestine, and only a fraction of what is absorbed can be converted to VA in our body (de Pee et al., 1995, 1998). Bioavailability of proVA carotenoids can be further impaired by factors such as excessive cooking, and absence of enhancers of absorption (e.g. fat) or presence of inhibitors of absorption (e.g. alcohol) in the meal, reducing the retinol equivalence of ingested carotenoids. Thus both insufficient dietary intake of VA and other factors related to bioavailability of proVA carotenoids are major determinants of VAD.

Ingested VA that is not used immediately can be stored in the body, mostly in the liver, and when necessary liver retinol is mobilized, bound to retinol-binding protein (RBP), via serum to supply physiological needs and, for mothers, breastmilk retinol. VAD occurs when liver stores of VA become depleted through insufficient dietary intake or through increased physiological requirements, or both. Clinical VAD can be diagnosed by night blindness (XN), eye lesions, and vision related tests. Subclinical VAD can be assessed with biochemical markers such as serum retinol and RBP.

Materials and Methods

Study Population: The study population is the Ariaal of Marsabit District in northern Kenya (see **Figure 1** for map). They traditionally practiced mixed-species semi-nomadic pastoralism (Fratkin, 1998; Sobania, 1988), but began to settle in large numbers following droughts throughout the 1970s and 1980s. Today, of approximately 10,000 Ariaal, about one half are permanently settled, making a living through economic opportunities as farmers, livestock and dairy traders, or wage earners, although many still continue to keep livestock where possible (Fratkin, 1991, Fratkin and Roth, 2005). Despite increasing integration in the market economy, Ariaal culture places a high value on livestock for food and ethnic pride, maintains strict observation to a complex age-set system, and practices a patrilineal, patrilocal, clan-based social system (Fratkin, 1991, 1998). In this society women have on average over 6 children during the course of reproductive span, spending a considerable time either pregnant or breastfeeding (Roth, 1994, 1999).

For the Ariaal biological concomitants of sedentism include reduced growth velocity (Fratkin et al., 1999; Nathan et al., 1996; Roth et al., 2005; Shell-Duncan and Obiero, 2000). Dietary practices of mothers and children in sedentary communities, such as low intake of foods from animal sources, are likely responsible for this negative impact on child growth (Fujita et al., 2005; Nathan et al., 1996). Local nurses report that childhood parasitic infections are common, while prevalence of infections, including HIV, among women is largely unknown.

Study Method: XN surveys were conducted in September 2004 among an availability sample of 37 mothers, and again in September 2005 among a separate availability sample of 15 breastfeeding mothers. All mothers in the 2004 survey had a child less than 3 years of age who may or may not have been breastfed at the time of survey (the survey did not specifically ask

mothers if they were currently breastfeeding their child). In contrast, all mothers in the 2005 survey were breastfeeding. A dietary recall survey was conducted in September 2005 with the 15 lactating mothers who also responded to the XN survey. Both 2004 and 2005 surveys were conducted during dry seasons when food and water were scarce in the area. However, the 2004 survey took place when food security was a very serious problem because seasonal rainfall had been near absent during this year (IRI, 2004). The problem of food security was less severe at the time of 2005 survey which took place a few months subsequent to the normal seasonal rainfall (NOAA, 2006).

For the assessment of XN, a WHO (1996) interview algorithm was used. This asked: 1) Do you have any problem seeing in the day time? 2) Do you have any problem seeing at night time? 3) If 2) is yes, is this problem different from other people in your community? 4) Do you have “tinimidolisho kwarie” or “modoki” (local terms for night blindness)? Validity of this algorithm is high with reasonable specificity when used with local terms of night blindness symptoms (WHO, 1996). A maternal XN prevalence of $\geq 5\%$ is a cut-off for the public health significance of VAD (IVACG, 2002).

For estimating typical patterns of maternal diet, a 24-hour dietary recall interview was used. Mothers were asked to report all foods that she consumed the previous day, to estimate the amount in common household units such as cups and spoons, and if this represented her typical diet. Portion sizes were quantified using food models and by filling local dishes and utensils with dried rice to the level specified by mothers. After listing all foods, information on the recipe was collected for any mixed dish recalled. Amounts of each ingredient in the recipe were estimated using food models and household utensils, and the amount of each ingredient consumed was estimated from her portion as a fraction of the total amount prepared. The resulting recall list of

foods and portion sizes in grams was entered into the SIGHT AND LIFE VA intake calculator. (Erhardt, 2003). This program estimated totals of energy, fat, retinol, and carotene intake while taking into consideration the bioavailability of VA in each meal.

Results

XN survey

Table 1 summarizes the prevalence of XN. This study defined XN if respondent reported all of the following conditions: 1) she has no problem seeing in the daytime, 2) she has problem seeing at night time, and 3) she suffers nightblindness. Based on this definition of XN, 27% and 20% of women reported XN at the 2004 and 2005 surveys, respectively. Since the prevalence of XN $\geq 5\%$ among pregnant women is a recommended cut-off of VAD as a public health problem, the data strongly indicate that VAD is public health problem in the study area.

Dietary Recall Data

Dietary recalls revealed that all women consumed predominantly maize and wheat-based diets which provide meager amount of VA. **Table 2** summarizes nutrient intake of breastfeeding women (N=15). Mean energy and VA intake were 1,440 Kcal and 74 μg , respectively. These are well below the recommended daily values for lactating women (2,600 Kcal and 1,200 μg , respectively; UNU/WHO, 1983). VA intake is especially low, reaching less than 10% of recommended value.

Summary and Discussion

This study collected maternal XN and dietary report data in an Ariaal agro-pastoral community of Karare. Results showed an extremely high prevalence of maternal XN and a very low dietary intake estimate of VA, indicating a high likelihood that the community has a serious

public health problem arising from VAD. These results are noteworthy since Karare was reported as a relatively successful community among several in the area with relatively well-balanced nutrient intake (Shell-Duncan and Yung, 2004). Thus Karare may serve as a good example in which a successful settlement of pastoralists can have “invisible” and yet detrimental nutritional consequences that can go unnoticed in studies solely dependent on anthropometric measurements.

While there is no comparative XN data from a nomadic Ariaal pastoral community, maternal dietary recall data from the pastoral community of Lewogoso are available from a previous study (Fujita, 2004, 2005). These indicate maternal diets heavily dependent on milk, except in times of food scarcity when pastoralists consume maize meal obtained through drought relief. Because foods of animal origin have higher and more readily absorbable VA than plant-based food (McLaren and Frigg, 2001), pastoralists who predominantly consume milk are less likely to suffer VAD, and we can hypothesize that the high prevalence of maternal XN in a settled community is a biological concomitant of settlement.

This hypothesis is consistent with previous studies showing impaired child growth in sedentary Ariaal and Rendille communities relative to a nomadic community (Fratkin et al., 1999; Nathan et al., 1996; Roth et al. 2005). Mothers with VAD produce breastmilk with low VA concentration through which children’s VA status will be compromised while in children VA is crucial for growth. Slower child growth in sedentary communities may be partly attributable to lower intake of VA by infant.

However, this study assessed XN only at the clinical level in small availability samples. Clinical VAD such as XN is only the tip of an iceberg beneath which a much larger proportion of people suffer subclinical VAD. Since subclinical VAD can have serious adverse effects on health,

the public health significance of VAD can be better delineated by including VA status assessment at the subclinical level. One-drop of blood from a finger prick suffices to estimate the serum retinol or RBP concentration to assess VAD at the subclinical level (for examples of such technology, see Erhardt et al., 2002; Hix et al., 2004). A follow-up study should fully investigate the prevalence of maternal VAD and associated factors in settled communities and also in a nomadic pastoral community by using a minimally-invasive assessment technology of finger-prick. This will facilitate improved understanding of the biological concomitant of sedentarization which may uncover possible “hidden hunger” caused by subclinical micronutrient deficiency.

Acknowledgements

This study was possible with financial support from the Puget Sound Partners for Global Health Travel Grant, and the University of Washington (UW) Graduate School Chester Fritz Fellowship. Computing and information resource support were provided by the Center for Studies in Demography and Ecology (CSDE) of UW. I thank my doctoral committee – Dr. Bettina Shell-Duncan, Dr. Jonathan Gorstein, Dr. Kathleen O’Connor, and Dr. Eric Roth – for their guidance and encouragement. My appreciation also goes to the generosity of Dr. Elizabeth Ngugi who facilitated my stay in Kenya, and Drs. Elliot Fratkin and Martha Nathan who provided me with an opportunity to present the earlier draft at the 2005 African Studies Association meeting. Finally, my sincere appreciation goes to Korea Leala and Antonella Lobra of Marsabit, and to all Ariaal women who participated in this study.

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Figure 1 Map of Northern Kenya

Table 1. Nightblindness (XN) in Karare

<i>Nightblindness (XN) Survey</i>		
<i>Year</i>	<i>2004 (drought)</i>	<i>2005 (dry)</i>
N=	37	15
Sample Criteria	Mothers with a child <3yr of age*	Breastfeeding mothers
XN prevalence	27% (10/37)	20% (3/15)

* Mothers in 2004 survey may or may not be breastfeeding.

Table 2. Nutrient intake by breastfeeding mothers in Karare (N=15)

<i>Nutrient</i>	<i>Mean (Std Dev¹) Range</i>	<i>RDA for lactating women²</i>
Energy (Kcal)	1440 (461) 787- 2474	Energy 2600 Kcal
Fat (g)	26.9 (18.4) 11 - 68	-----
Total VA (µg)	74.1 (28) 20 -134	Total VA 1200 µg
Retinol (µg)	19.2 (21.9) 0 - 72	-----
Carotene (µg)	676.8 (363) 20 - 1314	-----

Predominantly maize and wheat based diet provides meager amount of VA to mothers in Karare. Total VA is based on retinol and carotene intake where carotene conversion factor to VA of 12 has been used. SIGHT and LIFE VA intake calculator was used for nutrient analysis.

¹Standard deviation

² Recommended dietary allowance (RDA) values from UNU/FAO 1983